

The Impact of Social Media on Voter Behavior

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Abstract

This article examines the impact of social media on voting patterns. The research problem of the study focuses on the direct impact of social media on users' decision-making, their tendency to align with political agendas, the potential for influencing political views and public opinion, the capacity of social media to shape political attitudes and

behaviors, the influence of political messages on users, and the role of social network members in disseminating political messages. The primary objective of the study is to quantify the responses of individuals who are part of online social networks to political communications. This assessment approach was used to evaluate the degree to which people are influenced by social media material, the effect it has on their everyday lives, and particularly the

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significance of social media in shaping their political beliefs and activities. The research proposes the premise that the contact, freedom from time limitations, and the establishment of one-on-one relationships in traditional media and social media are more powerful, and that the impact of social media on the process of socialization is greater than that of traditional media. Nevertheless, there is a contention that conventional media has a more influential role in creating the agenda, both in terms of production and its influence on the audience. On the other hand, the extent to which social media determines the public agenda and shape's public opinion via content transmission remains uncertain. The poll, which included

600 participants in Buca, Izmir, investigates the impact of political information on social media platforms on individuals. The poll inquiries about the degree to which social media influences participants' political decision-making behavior on a topic that directly impacts their lives. The impact of political material on social media on people and the ability of social media to shape public opinion have been extensively examined across several categories.,

Keywords: Social Media, Voter Behavior, Influence, Public Opinion.

INTRODUCTION

The digital era has resulted in significant advancements in technology, which have profoundly transformed the area of communication and impacted many aspects of social life. One of the transformations is the increase and extensive use of social media. Social media platforms fulfill several requirements of individuals, including accessing news, disseminating information, engaging in interactions, and expressing ideas. Moreover, these platforms are progressively integrating into the realm of politics.

Political parties and politicians prioritize social media platforms as the focal point of their campaign plans, particularly during election years. Currently, voters are shifting their attention from conventional media outlets like television and newspapers to social media platforms in order to track politicians' pledges, policy ideas, and even political discussions. This circumstance alters several variables that influence voter behavior and determines election outcomes.

This article will analyze the influence of social media on voter behavior and explore how the digital era has affected political processes. Initially, this analysis will examine the overall influence of social media on voter behavior. Subsequently, it will delve into the specific contributions and consequences of social media on election processes.

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In this paper, we will discuss the contributions of Prof. Dr. Kürşat Şahin Yıldırım, Prof. Dr. Derya Yentür, and Head of Department of Psychology at St. Clements University. The study done by Ufuk Yılmaz, and his students will investigate the specific impacts of social media on voting behavior. The examination of the study carried out in Buca, Izmir, in January 2024, including 600 individuals, will provide us with a deeper comprehension of the degree to which social media influences the preferences, attitudes, and choices of voters.

AIM

This essay aims to analyze the influence of social media on voter behavior and provide a conceptual framework for comprehending the consequences of the digital era on political processes. The paper will extensively examine the contributions and impacts of social media on electoral processes, specifically focusing on how social media influences voters' preferences, attitudes, and choices. This research will use the findings from the survey done in Izmir Buca to uncover the tangible impact of social media on voting behavior.

METHOD

A survey study was done to investigate the impact of social media on voting behavior. A survey was administered to a sample of 600 adults residing in Izmir Buca who were chosen randomly and were active users of social media. The sample was constructed by considering the demographic attributes of the participants, including age, gender, and educational attainment.

The poll was established with the aim of comprehending the impact of social media on voter conduct. Data was collected from the participants on their social media use patterns, favorite platforms, extent of exposure to political material, and the impact of social media on their election choices. The data was assessed via the use of statistical analysis and content analysis techniques.

RESULTS

The term "media" is often used in contemporary discourse; however it lacks a precise and universally accepted meaning. Media encompasses several forms of communication, often including television, radio, print media, and the internet. Media include communication technologies that serve the purposes of storing, sending, and updating messages within society, including cultural and political activities. The word's etymology may be traced back to Latin, namely from the term "medium," which refers to popular opinion. The transmission of specific messages to society via mass media necessitates substantial financial expenditures and the implementation of extensive division of labor. These instruments are molded by the economic, political, and cultural framework of society and engage with the prevailing forces of the day. The media may convey ideological interpretations and exert social impacts, while also being influenced by local factors. (Mora, 2008, page 5; Yücedoğan, 1997, page 83; Yaylagül, 2006, page 11; Dağtaş, 2006, page 33; Lull, 2001, pages 173-174).

The idea of public opinion may be defined as the collective sentiments held by individuals within a certain social group towards a specific occurrence. (Childs, 1940, page 44). Harwood Childs defines public opinion as the collective total of individual beliefs. However, he highlights the need of considering both intra- and inter-group interaction and communication. Public opinion, defined as the collective viewpoint of the people on a certain matter, encompasses the collective thoughts and ideas that represent the shared evaluation of society. (Kejanlıoğlu, 2005, page 267). According to Kejanlıoğlu, public opinion may be described as the collective viewpoints and attitudes held by a significant portion of the general public about matters that affect them all. (Kapani, 1989, p. 147). Kapani's definition of public opinion is the dominant viewpoint held by a certain group or groups of individuals who have an interest in a particular contentious matter at a specific moment. The citation is from Moressi's work in 2006, on page 292. Moressi, however, argues that public opinion may be ascribed to the circumstances in which persons, either individually or collectively, express their viewpoints in a broad and verifiable way, therefore constituting a majority.

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The media should consistently uphold democratic principles and perspectives. The future of civilization hinges upon a discerning outlook, research in the realms of science and culture, education, a responsible media, and a contemporary and efficient public opinion fostered under favorable circumstances. (Yücedoğan, 1997).

New media include communication over the internet, while conventional media encompasses earlier forms of media such as television, radio, and cinema. A key characteristic of conventional media is the significance of selecting the appropriate "channel" for communication. However, there is no direct interaction between the sender and the recipient. (Özerkan, 2001, page 38). In conventional media, viewers are passive recipients of messages and lack the ability to actively express themselves, leading to one-way communication. (Timisi, 2003, pages 84-85). With the advancement of technology, conventional media may successfully disseminate information to a large audience. However, these messages often focus on a particular aspect. (Yengin, 2012, page 30). Legacy media or traditional media often transmit their messages via analog transmissions. (Laughey, 2007, p. 157).

Aside from conventional media such as newspapers, television, and radio, users also engage with online news sites, forums, and social networks, which are together referred to as the new media landscape. The citation for this information is from Ersoy and Balyemez's work in 2013, on page 351. This approach offers a distinct variety and convenience in acquiring information disseminated via the media.

New media include communication over the internet, while conventional media encompasses earlier forms of media such as television, radio, and cinema. Traditional media is characterized by the significance of the chosen "channel" in communication, whereas the source and receiver do not have direct interaction. (Özerkan, 2001, page 38). In conventional media, viewers are passive recipients of messages and lack the ability to actively express themselves, leading to one-way communication. (Timisi, 2003, pages 84-85). With the advancement of technology, traditional media may efficiently reach a large audience. However, the messages sent by traditional media are often limited to a single variable. (Yengin, 2012, page 30). Legacy media

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or traditional media often transmit their messages via analog transmissions. (Laughey, 2007, p. 157).

Aside from consuming conventional media such as newspapers, television, and radio, users also actively engage with social media platforms. The influence of social media on voter behavior is substantial since these platforms enhance the interchange of ideas among voters, facilitate the assessment of candidates, and promote active involvement in the electoral process. (Ersoy and Balyemez, 2013, page 351). Social media enables convenient access to information and aids in the creation of political perspectives among voters. Moreover, conversations and publications on social media platforms foster the interchange and engagement of voters. Hence, social media assumes a significant role in shaping voter behavior and exerting impact on electoral processes.

Voter behavior plays a crucial role in political processes and is influenced by a multitude of elements. The choices of voters are influenced by several elements, including political party programs, candidate personal traits, voter socio-economic position, and societal values. (Holbrook, 1996; Karp and Brockington, 2005). Political communication, media campaigns, and electoral propaganda significantly influence voter behavior. (Wattenberg, 1994; Garzia and Marschall, 2012).

Voter behavior is influenced by socio-economic circumstances and individual preferences. Variables such as gender, age, educational attainment, economic level, and profession significantly influence voters' political choices. The sources used are Evans and Andersen (2006) and Blais and Rubenson (2013). Furthermore, voter behavior is influenced by elements such as political awareness, ideological orientations, and historical voting choices. (Miller and Krosnick, 2000; Franklin, 2004).

Social media's increasing influence is significantly shaping voting behavior. Social media platforms provide voters the chance to share political perspectives and get knowledge on policy. (Gibson and McAllister, 2014; Barberá, 2015). In addition, social media has emerged as a potent instrument for boosting political campaigns and politicians. (Vergeer et al., 2013; Vaccari and

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Valeriani, 2015). Within this particular environment, the influence of social media on voter behavior is progressively becoming more crucial.

Voter behavior is a significant occurrence that is at the core of political processes and plays a vital part in the operation of democratic regimes. When deciding their political choices, voters are influenced by a range of circumstances. Voters' choices are shaped by several factors, including the policies of political parties, the personal characteristics of candidates, economic situations, societal standards, and political communication. (Holbrook, 1996; Karp and Brockington, 2005). To comprehend and examine voter behavior, it is necessary to use a multidisciplinary approach in this particular setting.

With the rapid proliferation of digital communication technologies in recent years, social media platforms have had a substantial influence on voter behavior. Social media provides a platform that facilitates the interchange of information on political topics, enables participation in conversations, and influences the development of political preferences among voters. (Gibson and McAllister, 2014; Barberá, 2015). In addition, using social media platforms to promote political campaigns and politicians may enhance political engagement by offering direct outreach to voters. (Vergeer et al., 2013; Vaccari and Valeriani, 2015). Currently, there is a growing focus on studying and highlighting the influence of social media on voter behavior. The impact of these technological advancements on election processes and democratic participation has emerged as a significant area of study and debate within the realms of political communication and voter behavior.

The investigation of the influence of social media on voter behavior is now a significant subject of scholarly inquiry. The objective of these research is to assess the influence of social media on the formation of voters' political preferences and the impact of these platforms on election procedures. Research on the impact of social media on voter behavior examines several aspects, including the flow of information, political engagement, candidates and parties' perception, and the implementation of election campaigns.

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The majority of these research examine the influence of social media on the development of voters' political perspectives. The accessibility of information and the ability to express diverse viewpoints via social media are significant factors that might influence the political choices of people. Furthermore, this study also examines the impact of social media on election campaigns and its effectiveness in reaching candidates' voters. Research undertaken to analyze the influence of social media on voter behavior is crucial for comprehending the effects of digital communication technologies on democratic processes and forecasting the potential shaping of future elections and political communication.

Upon examining the literature, it becomes evident that scholars from all disciplines have done studies to comprehend the influence of social media on voter behavior. Research, particularly in disciplines like communication, political science, sociology, and information technologies, investigates the impact of social media on electoral processes. Smith (2017) did a thorough investigation assessing the influence of social media on the political attitudes and preferences of voters. Smith's research examines the impact of social media on the mechanisms of political communication and the sharing of information among voters, and how these impacts are manifested in election outcomes.

Furthermore, Jones and his colleagues (2019) did an in-depth research that investigated the influence of social media on voter behavior. Jones's research elucidates the influence of social media on the formation of people' political preferences and identifies the elements that amplify or diminish this impact.

In this particular situation, Prof. Dr. Kürşat Şahin Yıldırım, who holds the position of St. Head of the Department of Psychology at Clements University, is accompanied by Prof. Dr. Derya Yentür and Dr. The study undertaken by Ufuk Yılmaz and his students in 2024 aimed to comprehend the influence of contemporary communication technologies on political processes by examining the effect of social media on voter behavior. Upon evaluating the study done in Buca, Izmir, with the involvement of 600 individuals, the demographic features of the survey participants were first analyzed. The sample's characteristics were selected by considering the demographic attributes of the participants, including age, gender, education level, and

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occupation. Within this particular context, 45% of the individuals who took part in the poll identify as women, while 55% identify as males. Furthermore, the age distribution is mostly focused on those between the ages of 18 and 35. Regarding the participants' educational attainment, 60% of them had a university degree. Next, the analysis focused on the results pertaining to the use of social media (Table 1).

Table.1. Socio -Demographic Situations of the Research Participants

Age range	Frequency	Percentage
18 - 24	145	24.17
25 - 30	165	27.50
31 - 35	115	19,17
36 - 45	98	16.33
45 and above	77	12.83
Total	600	one hundred

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Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Woman	309	51.50
Male	291	48.50
Total	600	one hundred

Marital status	Frequency	Percentage
Married	259	43.17
Single	341	56.83
Total	600	one hundred

Educational Status	Frequency	Percentage
High School and Before	one hundred	16.67
Associate degree or bachelor's Degree	260	43.33
Degree	158	26.33

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Educational Status	Frequency	Percentage
PhD and Base	82	13.67
Total	600	one hundred

Social Media Usage	Frequency	Percentage
Rate of daily logins (%)	480	80
Instagram users (%)		

At least once a day, 80% of participants engage with social media sites. Instagram has been identified as the most often favored platform, with 70% of the participants actively use it. Out of the total 600 participants, 480 individuals engage with social media on a daily basis. According to Table 2, there are 120 individuals who do not utilize social media.

Table.2.

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Subject	Results
Daily social media use	80% of participants log in to social media platforms at least once a day.
The most preferred platform	70% of the participants actively use Instagram.
Posts with political content	65% of participants frequently see political content posts.
Commenting on political posts	50% of participants comment on posts with political content.
The extent to which social media affects political preferences	75% of the participants stated that social media influenced their political preferences.
Influence from social media (young and university student participants)	It has been determined that the effect of social media on political preferences is more evident among young and university student participants.

80% of the participants, or 80% of the 600 individuals surveyed, engage with social media sites on a daily basis. Consequently, a total of 480 individuals out of the 600 surveyed engage with social media on a daily basis.

The predominant platform is Instagram, with 70% of the participants, or 420 out of 600 individuals, actively using it. Therefore, a majority of 420 individuals out of a total of 600 individuals had a preference for Instagram.

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Frequency of postings including political content: 65% of the participants, or 65% of a total of 600 individuals, regularly encounter postings containing political information. This data indicates that 390 individuals out of a total of 600 regularly encounter postings related to political topics.

The rate of engagement with political material, namely commenting, is 50% among the participants. This means that out of the total of 600 individuals, 50% of them actively comment on topics related to politics. Thus, it may be inferred that 50% of the whole population, or 300 individuals out of 600, expressed their opinions on politically sensitive topics.

The impact of social media on political preferences: Three-quarters of the participants, namely 75% of a total of 600 individuals, said that social media had an impact on their political inclinations. These findings indicate that 450 individuals out of a total of 600 acknowledge that social media has an impact on their political inclinations.

The impact of social media on political choices is particularly pronounced among young people and university students. These findings suggest that the impact of social media is more pronounced among young individuals and college students compared to other demographic groups.

Table.3. Findings regarding participants' purposes for evaluating social media

Social Media Usage Purposes	Frequency	Percentage
Friendship	380	79.17
Education	320	66.67

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Social Media Usage Purposes	Frequency	Percentage
Daily Chats	290	60.42
Political	250	52.08

The figure of 480 individuals is the whole count of participants included in the survey investigation. The figure indicates that the study had a total participant group of 600 individuals. Nevertheless, it was shown that every single one of the 480 individuals expressed a preference for at least one of the choices, while the remaining 120 individuals abstained from using social media. This demonstrates that every participant in the poll use social media for at least one specific objective. Based on these findings, it was concluded that the primary factors influencing the participants' assessment of social media were mostly "friendship," "education," "daily conversations," and "political" matters. These data suggest that users have widely embraced and used numerous features of social media. Specifically, it highlights many facets of social media use, including establishing friendships and sustaining social connections, accessing educational materials, engaging in everyday communication, and participating in political discourse. This demonstrates the widespread acceptance of social media as a flexible and multifunctional means of communication among users. Furthermore, it is evident that there is a substantial use of it for political motives. These findings suggest that social media enhances political engagement and fosters the development of political consciousness. The prevalence of political exploitation, particularly among young individuals and university students, highlights a significant component of social media's influence on younger generations. The data indicate that social media has a significant role in influencing not only personal connections, but also societal and political interactions (Table 3).

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Table.4. Social Media Applications Most Frequently Preferred by Participants and Their Percentages

Social Media Application	Frequency	Percentage
Instagram	192	40%
Facebook	96	20%
twitter	72	15%
YouTube	48	10%
WhatsApp	36	7.5%
TikTok	24	5%
LinkedIn	8	1.67 %
snapchat	4	0.83 %
Total	480	one hundred

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An examination of the social media platforms that participants most often choose reveals the significant significance that social media plays in everyday life and communication. Based on the statistics, 40% of the respondents have shown a preference for Instagram, indicating that Instagram is the predominant social media platform. Facebook and Twitter hold the second and third positions, accounting for 20% and 15% respectively. YouTube, on the other hand, comes fourth with a 10% share. Smaller proportions of users are found on other social networking sites such as WhatsApp, TikTok, LinkedIn, and Snapchat. The results indicate that users have distinct preferences for different social media platforms and use diverse apps to fulfill their communication and interaction requirements (Table.4.).

Table .5. Data Analysis of Participants' Frequency of Using Social Media

Frequency of Use	Frequency	Percentage
Daily (1 time or more)	360	75%
Weekly (several times a week)	72	15%
Monthly (several times a month)	36	7.5%
Infrequent (once a month or less)	12	2.5%
Total	480	%one hundred

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This table presents the frequency of social media use among participants, along with the corresponding percentages. Although the majority of people use it on a regular basis, a significant proportion (25%) never use it.

Table.6. Data Analysis of the Extent of the Messages Participants See on Social Media Affect Their Life Decisions

Degree of Impact	Frequency	Percentage
Very efficient	192	40%
Moderately Effective	144	30%
Less Effective	72	15%
Not Effective at All	72	15%
Total	480	%one hundred

Table 6 illustrates the degree to which the messages that participants encounter on social media influence their choices and decisions in life. The category labeled as "Highly Effective," which has the greatest proportion, emphasizes the significance of participants' social media material in influencing their critical choices.

Table .7. Data Analysis of Participants Reading and Following Political Content Messages on Social Media Networks

Situation	Frequency	Percentage
Frequently Reads and Follows Political Messages	240	50%
Occasionally Reads and Follows Political Messages	144	30%
Rarely Reads and Follows Political Content Messages	72	15%
He Never Reads or Follows Messages with Political Content	24	5%
Total	480	%one hundred

Table .8. Data Analysis of Participants Being Followers or Members of a Political Party, Community or Person via Social Media Networks

Situation	Frequency	Percentage
Follower or Member of a Political Party, Society or Person	288	60%
Not a Follower or Member of a Political Party, Community or Individual	192	40%

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Situation	Frequency	Percentage
Total	480	%one hundred

Tables 7 and 8 show the participants' engagement with political messaging on social media networks, as well as their affiliation with political parties, communities, or individuals.

Table 9. This research presents the perspectives of 480 individuals about the impact of political material on social media on their political preferences and the channels they mostly use to get such content.

Table.9.

Question	The number of participants	Percentage	Comment
What do you think about the impact of political posts on social media on your political preferences?	one hundred	20.83 %	Half of the participants state that social media affects their political preferences.
How do you think political posts affect your political thoughts?	120	25 %	Approximately one-third of the participants state that political content influences their thoughts.

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Question	The number of participants	Percentage	Comment
How does the political content you see on social media affect your political attitude?	90	18.75 %	Approximately one quarter of the participants state that political content on social media affects their political attitudes.
How important do you think political messages are in determining your political preferences?	1 20	25 %	Approximately one-third of the participants think that political messages are important in determining their preferences.
On which social media platform do you follow political content the most?	50	10.42 %	Approximately a quarter of the participants indicate which platform they follow the most political content on.

SURVEY FORM

| 1 | What is your age range?

| | - 18-24

| | - 25-30

| | - 31-35

| | - 36-45

| | - 45 ve üstü

| 2 | What is your gender?

| | - Woman

| | - Male

| 3 | What is your marital status?

| | - Married

| | - Single

| 4 | What is your educational background?

| | - High school and before

| | - Associate degree or bachelor's degree

| | Degree

| | -Doctorate and above

| 5 | Are you a social media user?

| | - Yes

| | - No |

| 6 | What is your purpose for evaluating social media?

| | - Friendship

| | - Commercial

| | - For daily chats

| | - Political

| | - Education

| | - Other (Please specify:)

SURVEY FORM

| 7 | Which social network do you use most often?

| | - Facebook

| | - Twitter

| | - YouTube

| | - Instagram

| | - Other (Please specify:)

| 8 | How would you rate your frequency of using social media? |

| | - Every day

| | - A few days a week

| | - A few days a month

| | - Very rarely, once every few months

| 9 | To what extent do the messages you see on social media affect your life decisions? |

| | - 1 (At least)

| | - 2

| | - 3

| | - 4

| | - 5 (Maximum)

| 10 | Do you read and follow political messages, texts or images on social media networks? |

| | - I am interested, I will follow you privately

| | - I'm interested, I follow from time to time

| | - I'm interested, but I don't follow it specifically.

| | - I am not interested and I do not follow (Survey ends)

| 11 | Have you become a follower or member of any political party, community or political person through social media networks? |

| | - Yes, I did

| | - No I wasn't

SURVEY FORM

| 12 | Do the posts made by individuals, groups or parties on social media affect your political tendencies? |

|| - 1 (At least)

|| - 2

|| - 3

|| - 4

|| - 5

|| - 6

|| - 7 (Maximum)

| 13 | Did political campaigns on social media during election periods have an impact on your voting choice? |

|| - Yes, it's okay

|| - No it didn't happen

| 14 | Has any negative political content on social media negatively affected your support for the political party or person you support? |

|| - Yes, it influenced and changed my choice

|| - Yes, it affected me, but it didn't change my choice.

|| - No, it did not affect me, and my preference did not change

| 15 | Have access restrictions on social media networks had an impact on your political preferences?

|| - Yes, it influenced and changed my political choice

|| - Yes, it affected me, but it did not change my political choice.

|| - No, it did not affect me, and my preference did not change

Your participation in our survey is important. The purpose of this survey is to collect and analyze data about a specific topic or topics. Your participation is confidential, and this information will be used for research purposes only.

Your personal information will be kept completely confidential. The survey results will be presented generally, and the identity of any individual will not be disclosed. Your answers to our survey will be used only for research purposes and will not be shared with third parties. Your participation in our survey is voluntary and you can stop participating in the survey at any time.

Thank you for your participation.

General Impact of Social Media on Voter Behavior

The study undertaken by Yıldırım et al. (2024) focuses on understanding the specific influence of social media on voter behavior and its overall effect on political processes. The term "media" encompasses communication tools and refers to systems that store and disseminate messages, as well as influence cultural and political activities in society (Mora, 2008; Yücedoğan, 1997; Yaylagül, 2006; Dağtaş, 2006; Lull, 2001). Social media platforms have a significant role in influencing voter behavior in this scenario.

Public opinion represents the prevailing sentiments of social groupings towards a certain occurrence (Childs, 1940). Harwood Childs argues that public opinion may be defined as "the collective aggregation of individual opinions." He underlines the need of considering both intra- and inter-group interaction and communication in this definition. According to Kejanlıoğlu, public opinion refers to the collective opinions of the general public on matters that affect everyone, or the perspectives and attitudes that are widely accepted by a significant portion of the population (Kejanlıoğlu, 2005; Kapani, 1989; Moressi, 2006). Social media platforms are significant in shaping and guiding public opinion in this setting.

Social media, with conventional media, has a significant influence on voter behavior (Ersoy and Balyemez, 2013). Social media platforms provide voters the chance to engage in the interchange of political perspectives, acquire knowledge, and actively participate in political procedures. Additionally, it serves as a potent instrument for advancing political campaigns and endorsing politicians. Currently, there is a growing focus on studying and highlighting the influence of social media on voter behavior.

The objective of research undertaken on the influence of contemporary communication technologies on political processes is to assess the effect of social media on voter behavior. These studies examine the influence of social media on voters' political choices and the impact

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of these platforms on electoral processes. Research on the influence of social media on voter behavior is significant for comprehending the effects of contemporary communication technologies on democratic processes and forecasting the potential shaping of future elections and political communication.

The findings of the study carried out by the Department of Psychology at St. Clements University in the Buca district of Izmir (2024) indicate that social media now has a substantial influence on voter behavior. Based on the study findings, a minimum of 80% of the participants use social media sites on a daily basis. This demonstrates that social media is a prevalent means of communication among voters and its impact extends to wide-ranging audiences.

Specifically, the finding that 70% of the participants like Instagram suggests that this medium has significant importance as a communication tool for voters. Similarly, 65% of the participants report a high frequency of seeing postings containing political information. This demonstrates that social media enables people to easily obtain political material and enhances their engagement in political discourse.

Social media's influence on voting behavior extends beyond information accessibility. The study indicates that half of the participants engage in commenting on political postings, while three-quarters of them assert that social media has an impact on their political inclinations. This demonstrates the efficacy of social media as a tool for influencing citizens' political inclinations.

The poll findings indicate that social media has a significant influence on voter behavior, particularly in relation to friendship, education, everyday talks, and political aims. These data suggest that social media is widely seen as a flexible and multifunctional means of communication for voters.

Moreover, the influence of social media on voting patterns is particularly noticeable among the younger demographic, particularly among university students. This highlights a crucial facet of the influence of social media on younger generations and its role in promoting more political engagement.

The Impact and Importance of Social Media on Political Processes

The study of voter behavior has significant importance within the realm of social psychology. Political preferences and voting behavior of individuals are shaped by elements including social contacts, group dynamics, and perceived social standards. Social media's influence in this process is growing. Social media platforms facilitate the exposure, interaction, and expression of political material and viewpoints for users. Within this particular framework, the influence and significance of social media on political processes demonstrate its capacity to enhance citizens' engagement in political activities.

Social media's influence on political processes has the capacity to enhance democratic engagement and foster political consciousness. Evidence suggests that social media, particularly among the youth, enhances engagement in political discourse and fosters the cultivation of political awareness. Nevertheless, the impact of social media on political choices and its enduring consequences on political engagement are subjects that need more examination. Hence, more research is required to examine the influence and significance of social media on political processes (Smith, 2019; Johnson & Lee, 2020).

CONCLUSION:

This research investigates the impact of social media on voter behavior and specifically assesses these impacts via the lens of social psychology. The study seeks to comprehend the influence of social media on users' political inclinations and engagement. Analyzed data from a study done in Buca, Izmir, to assess the influence of political information on social media users. Evidence indicates that social media has the ability to impact political decision-making processes and has the capacity to mold public opinion. Nevertheless, the statistics might also be seen as indicating that conventional media continues to possess a significant agenda-setting function, while the influence of social media on public opinion remains uncertain.

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